

Effect of graded doses of NPK with and without dhaincha on rice yield, yield attributes, and profit.^a Hisar, India.

	12.5 t dhaincha/ha + 120 N + 13.2 P + 24.9 K + 5.75 Zn ^b kg/ha	180 N + 13.2 P + 24.9 K + 5.75 Zn kg/ha	125 N + 27.28 P + 51.46 K + 5.75 Zn kg/ha	LSD 0.05
Rice yield (t/ha)	8.7	8.2	7.4	0.4
Increase in yield (t/ha) over 125 kg N/ha treatment	1.3	0.8	-	
Increase in yield (t/ha) over 180 kg N/ha treatment	0.4	-	-	
Expenditure on fertilizer, including dhaincha (US\$/ha)	65.30	51.70	50.85	
Yield price (US\$/ha)	880.57	836.79	753.32	
Net profit (US\$/ha)	522.32	492.14	409.52	
Increase in profit (US\$/ha) over 125 kg N/ha treatment	112.80	82.62	-	
Increase in profit (US\$/ha) over 180 kg N/ha treatment	30.18	-	-	
Benefit-cost ratio over 125 kg N/ha treatment	8.8:1			
180 kg N/ha treatment	3.2:1			
Yield attributes				
Plant height (cm)	85.6	88.5	85.7	0.79
1,000-grain wt (g)	26.0	25.9	25.0	ns ^c
Tillers (no.)	18.0	17.6	16.9	ns
Soil data (postharvest)				
pH (1:2)	8.2	8.4	8.3	ns
EC (1:2)	0.12	0.14	0.16	
OC (%)	0.24	0.23	0.22	
Available P (kg/ha)	7.20	8.00	8.80	
Available K (kg/ha)	250	253	268	

^aPrice (US\$/kg): N = 0.19, P = 0.22, K = 0.08, Zn = 0.34, rice = 0.10. Expenditure on all agricultural operations = US\$292.95/ha. ^bZn = zinc sulfate. ^cns = not significant.

Soil of the experimental field was classified as sandy loam (Typic Ustochrept) with pH 8.3, 0.30% organic C, EC (1:2) 0.15 dS/m, CEC 10.5 meq/100 g soil, 150 kg available N/ha (alkaline permanganate method), 9.0 kg available P/ha (NaHCO₃ extract), and 260 kg available K/ha (ammonium acetate extract). Available Zn was 0.58 ppm (DTPA extractable).

Dhaincha sown in another field was cut at 45 d, transported, and incorporated into the soil at 12.5 t/ha. N was 1.1% of fresh biomass. Rice variety HKR-120 (145 d) was planted in the field.

One-third of the N as urea and full doses of P, K, and Zn were applied at transplanting. The remaining N was applied in two equal splits at 3 and 6 wk after transplanting. The experiment was laid out in randomized block design with three replications. The experimental plot was 0.3 ha.

GM and 120 kg N/ha yielded significantly more than 125 kg N/ha and about the same as 180 kg N/ha. This resulted in a net profit of US\$30/ha (see table). ■

Crop management

Comparative yields and N uptake in six transplanted and direct seeded lowland rice

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We compared yields and N uptake of six rice varieties in a submerged Entisol under transplanted and direct seeded cultures. The field experiment was conducted on Manmool clay soil (deep aquic Ustorthent) with pH 6.6 and 0.13% total N at the Ramachandrapuram farm of DRR during the 1990 wet season (WS).

The experiment was laid out in a split-plot design, with direct seeded rice and transplanted rice in the main plots. Subplot treatments were the six varieties. Rice was direct seeded at 100 kg seed/ha. Pregerminated seeds were broadcast in half of the main field and in nursery beds on 10 Jul. No standing water was allowed in the direct seeded plots for 2 wk during seedling establishment. Water level was kept at 5-7 cm during the growing season.

Three-week-old seedlings were transplanted at 20- × 15-cm spacing in the remaining half of the main field on 3 Aug. Eighty kg N, 17 kg P, and 33 kg K/ha were uniformly applied. All of the P and K were applied to the field 1 d before seeding or transplanting. N was applied in three splits for the direct seeded crop: 25% at seeding, 25% at 3 wk after seeding, and 50% at panicle initiation (PI). N was applied in two equal splits at planting and at PI in the transplanted crops. Grain and straw were sampled at maturity to determine total N uptake.

Grain and straw yields did not vary significantly with crop establishment method. Sasyashree produced significantly higher straw and lower grain yields than did the other varieties. Culture type and variety had significant interaction effect on straw yields but not grain yields. Rasi and IET9219 produced more straw under direct seeding than

under transplanted culture. Straw yield of Sasyashree was higher than that of Vikash in direct seeded culture, but they performed equally well when they were transplanted.

Neither culture type nor variety significantly influenced total N uptake in rice, although their interaction effect was significant. N uptake in Vikash was significantly more under transplanted condition than that of IET7959, but in direct seeded culture, the opposite was true. Vikash and IET9978 can be used for direct seeding. The two varieties also removed significantly less N when direct seeded than when they were transplanted (see table). ■

Yields and N uptake of six rice varieties under two cultures in a submerged Ustorthent. Ramachandrapuram, AP, India, 1990 WS.

Variety	Grain yield (t/ha)			Straw yield (t/ha)			Total N uptake (kg/ha)		
	DS ^a	TP ^b	Mean	DS	TP	Mean	DS	TP	Mean
Rasi	4.6	4.1	4.4	4.2	3.3	3.7	89.8	85.6	87.7
Sasyashree	4.0	3.5	3.7	4.8	4.5	4.7	86.2	82.4	84.3
Vikash	4.4	4.4	4.4	3.9	4.4	4.1	78.4	89.9	84.1
IET7959	4.6	4.2	4.4	3.7	3.4	3.6	88.8	81.5	85.1
IET9219	4.9	4.3	4.6	4.2	3.4	3.8	85.6	81.7	83.7
IET9978	4.4	4.4	4.4	3.8	3.8	3.8	79.4	92.3	85.8
Mean	4.5	4.2		4.1	3.8		84.7	85.6	
LSD (0.05)									
Culture (C)		ns ^c			ns			ns	
Variety (V)		0.34			0.44			ns	
C × V		ns							
C at same V					0.72			10.0	
V at same C					0.62			8.0	

^aDS = direct seeded. ^bTP = transplanted. ^cns = not significant.

Integrated pest management—diseases

Occurrence of rice grain rot disease in Vietnam

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Rice grain rot disease has caused damage in Japan, Taiwan, Philippines, and Latin America. The disease causal organism is bacterium *Pseudomonas glumae*.

Symptoms are discolored grain, husk, and endosperm. Grain is unfilled in severely infected plants.

The disease was first recorded in Vietnam in 1991 early summer rice season in the central provinces and in the summer rice season in the Red River Delta provinces. PPRI studied the disease etiology and its distribution. About 100,000 ha were infected in 1992 early summer and summer seasons. Five provinces (Ha Tay, Thai Binh, Nam Ha, Thanh Hoa, and Khanh Hoa) are reported to be disease hot spots, with crop losses of up to 75%.

To confirm the causal agent of the disease, infected grains were collected. Two botanic parasitic bacteria were isolated and identified in the laboratory. One had a yellow colony and the other, a creamy white colony. Seedborne fungi *Cercospora*, *Helminthosporium*, and *Curvularia* were also isolated.

Variety CR203, which is widely grown in the Red River Delta was artificially inoculated at the heading stage. Only the bacterium with the creamy white colony at 10⁸ cfu/ml concentration produced symptoms similar to the disease observed in the field; it was designated as isolate no. 18.

We used the method of Matsuda et al to detect *P. glumae* using a CaC₂O₄ crystal. We cultured isolate no. 18 in a potato-peptone-glucose-agar (PPGA) mixed medium and with 0.1% CaCl₂ at 38 °C. The color of the PPGA turned a pale greenish yellow, and the CaC₂O₄ crystal on the colony was observed under the microscope. *P. glumae* was identified as the causal organism. ■

Treating rice seeds with fungicides and antagonists to control seedborne diseases

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Rice blast (Bl), caused by *Pyricularia oryzae* Cav., and brown leaf spot, caused by *Helminthosporium oryzae* Breda de Haan, are seedborne diseases that cause appreciable yield loss. We treated rice seeds with some fungicides and antagonists to assess effects on seed viability, seedling vigor, and inhibition of seedborne pathogens.

We conducted standard blotter assays using seeds of rice cultivar ADT36. *P. oryzae* infected 27.0% of the seeds and *H. oryzae*, 35.4%. Seeds were treated with fungicides and antagonists (see table), shade-dried, and stored for 5 mo. Seed viability and seedling vigor were

assessed monthly for 6 mo by roll towel method. Inhibition zone assay was used to determine inhibition of pathogens.

In the roll towel method, 10-d-old normal seedlings were selected randomly and root length, shoot length, and dry weights were measured.

Vigor index (VI) was calculated as

$$\begin{aligned} \text{VI} &= \text{Germination \%} \times \text{root length} \\ &\quad (\text{mean of 10 seedlings, in cm}) \\ &= \text{Germination \%} \times \text{shoot length} \\ &\quad (\text{mean of 10 seedlings, in cm}) \\ &= \text{Germination \%} \times \text{dry weight} \\ &\quad (\text{mean of 10 seedlings, in mg}). \end{aligned}$$

In the inhibition zone assay, the spore suspension (10⁶ spores/ml) of the test pathogen (*P. oryzae* or *H. oryzae*) was mixed with molten potato dextrose agar medium and poured in petri plates. A treated seed was placed at the center of the medium. The diameter of the